

Use of Social Networking Sites in Libraries and Knowledge Center

Inam Magsi

M.Phil Scholar and Teaching Assistant Department of Library Information Science
University of Sindh Jamshoro
inam.magsi@usindh.edu.pk

Dr. Muhammad Akhtar Rind

Librarian, Allama I. I. kazi Central Library University of Sindh Jamshoro.
makhrind@usindh.edu.pk

Adnan Magsi

Lecturer, University of Sindh Jamshoro
adnan.magsi@usindh.edu.pk

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to explore the use of social networking sites by the librarians and information centers. The study is based on the literature review. In order to get to inference the following objectives were analyzed: 1. To identify the purpose of using Social Networking Sites by libraries and information center. 2. To know the benefits of Social Networking Sites. 3. To investigate the problems being faced by librarians using Social Networking Sites. In order to achieve the objectives of the study various papers of various authors have been observed, explored and thoroughly studied. It was explored that the most of the papers have revealed that social media networking sites are used to be in touch with the libraries and librarians so that the demands of the users may be fulfilled. It was also revealed that social media is a strong new way of communication, and the number of users famous on social media sites are rapidly increasing and the social media networking sites are useful for getting information remotely. The authors have identified and explored that social media networking sites are very useful to get relevant information on request. It was also observed that the social networking sites are good to make social and academic relations in educational environment. The study further investigated that time is precious to provide latest information to library users the libraries face power outage / electricity problems to be connected with the users. It further revealed that it is difficult to use social media networking sites in remote areas where there is no electricity and internet connectivity. Keeping in view the studies it has been suggested that to fulfill the requirement of the common people, the remote areas be connected via internet and ensure the use of the social media networking sites like Facebook, YouTube LinkedIn, twitter, WhatsApp to get the latest information and be connected with the world.

Keywords: social media, social networking sites, Networking Libraries, Information centers,

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Introduction

Academic and Mass media researchers are increasingly drawn to social networking sites (SNSs) because of their low cost and no difficulty of use. Because of the growing popularity of social networking services like Facebook, WhatsApp, twitter, link den, and other social media platforms provide libraries with new options. According to Suraweere et al. (2011), social networking is the way people interact in the twenty-first century. The phrase "social networking" refers to the act of developing relationships among a group of individuals who have a common interest. Social networking sites are web-based services that enable users to create a public or semi-public profile inside a circumscribed system, articulate a list of other users with whom they have a connection, and browse and navigate their list of connections as well as those produced by others within the system. The nature and terminology of these relationships may differ from one location to the next. Users of social networking sites may build a personalized account that contains information such as their date of birth, hobbies, preferences, education status, relationship status, and personal interests, among other things. Zywica and Danowski (2008), Social media is a strong new way of communication, and the number of users famous on social media sites is rapidly increasing. Because of its availability, social media platforms are used by millions of individuals in their daily lives for work, study, and recreation. Academic libraries throughout the world have discovered that social media may be used as an effective communication tool to communicate with teachers, staff, and students in interesting ways in order to reach students.

Meaning and Definitions

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Social networking is a platform that allows people to connect with one another or to exchange news, images, videos, and other online activities with others (Chakraborty,2020). The Cambridge Dictionary states that social networking is "the action of communicating and exchanging information with groups of people online, particularly through websites created specifically for this function.

According to Boyd, D. M., & Ellison, N. B. (2007) People utilize an online platform known as a social networking service or SNS (sometimes referred to as a social networking site) to develop social networks or social relationships with other individuals who share similar personal or professional information, interests, hobbies, backgrounds, or real-life connections. This type of platform can also be termed a social networking site.

Social Networking Sites and Libraries

Social networking in this age of information has a number of distinctive aspects that, when combined with the resources at hand, can enhance the library. As is well known, library users' attitudes are evolving daily. Despite the fact that SNSs are mostly used for leisurely contact with friends and family. However, they also offer unique and efficient ways for users to communicate with them. Social networking platforms are supplying the information community with timely and pertinent information. Therefore, libraries should step up and adopt this new technology, as well as try out some of the key SNS features like easy surfing, private messaging, increased participation, blogging, discussion forums, social collaboration, interactive learning, media and multimedia, event management, and so forth(Deepmala,2014). Social networking websites give users a place online where they may express their ideas and

engage in a range of activities (Kim et al., 2011). With the use of SNSs, libraries may reach out to their customers, and librarians can establish relationships and participate in their communities.

Literature Review

Kumar and Kumar (2013) ~~the~~ published a paper titled "Use of Social Networking Sites (SNSs):Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, India A Study to Investigate the Activities and Reasons for Users' Use of Social Networking Sites. A self-structured questionnaire was delivered to the target audience, and the major data collected through the questionnaire was analyzed and discussed in line with the study's goals. The majority of respondents were found to be aware of and use such programs in their research work. Facebook is the most popular SNS among all types of students and researchers.

Lee, Chen and Chan (2017) this research subject for an investigation on the usage of social media and the participation of college students in large-scale protest campaigns. The provided an explanation of the theoretical model, which supported the overall behavior. This study satisfies the criteria based on the empirical nature of its nature. In order to finish their research piece, they interviewed 795 college students and collected data from those interviews. The purpose of this research is to determine the level of prospective awareness of social networking sites.

Munshi, S. A., Mostafa, M., & Alam, M. (2018) This study examined how postgraduate students at the University of Rajshahi in Bangladesh use social media for education. The descriptive survey and questionnaire showed that students like social media for academic purposes. Most respondents chose Facebook, the most popular

SNS. This poll found that respondents felt SNSs provide current information and allow them to express ideas. SNSs are great for collaborative study, according to 90% of respondents.

Anwar. M and Tang chiwei (2019) studied that the social networking sites among university of Baluchistan student's participation in modern and digital era of social networking sites. This study used descriptive survey method. They have collected data 205 questionnaire distributed among the students. They find out 82% male using social media.

Chakraborty, K. (2020) examined Social networking websites are a key component of modern technology. whose importance is expanding quickly. Users were able to access information quickly because to social networking sites. SNS creates an environment where people may communicate their ideas online. For a study, various techniques may be employed. Data were gathered for this investigation using a questionnaire method. Social media is mostly used by students. As a result, if a library uses SNS, users are informed of library activities

Objectives of Study

1. To identify the purpose of using Social Networking Sites by libraries ;
2. To Know the benefits of Social Networking Sites by libraries
3. To investigate the problems being faced by librarians using Social Networking Sites;.

1. Use of Social Networking Sites in Libraries

In order to better serve their patrons, libraries can now take advantage of SNS. Librarians leverage social networking sites to "be part of their communities" and publicize their offerings. Research has shown that this is the case (Hendrix, Chiarelli, Hausman, Murphy, & Saffron; Chernigov & Barnett-Ellis, 2007). Some libraries use Twitter as a means of communicating with major information providers. Research shows that college students find using Facebook in library settings to be intriguing (Mack, Behler, Roberts, & Rimland, 2007). Social networking sites (SNSs) have been utilized in social science research to solicit answers from objects in the field and compile expert information (Poynter). (Salihu & Dahiru, 2023) Social networking sites (with their millions of users) provide libraries new opportunities to engage with communities and gain insight from user-librarian dialogue. Through a collaborative online forum, library patrons can share their insights and help shape the future of library services (Casey & Savastinuk). (Khaskheli & Siddiqui, 2022) The following are examples of SNS that librarians frequently employ to fulfill their patrons' informational requests:

Facebook

It is the current favorite among librarians because of all the useful features it offers, such as World Cat and JSTOR search (Kandare & Khan, 2022). Users can tell librarians exactly what they need in terms of information by contacting them directly. There are specialized library apps, and some of them are connected to Facebook by libraries.

WhatsApp

WhatsApp was founded by Jan Koum and Brian Acton after they spent 20 years working together at Yahoo. Despite integrating with Facebook in 2014, WhatsApp has remained a stand-alone application with a sharp focus on offering a messaging service that is quick and dependable everywhere. WhatsApp Communication is a mobile application that requires both participants to have the proprietary software installed on their mobile phones in order to operate. It also needs a mobile internet connection. WhatsApp also gives its users access to other social data, such as the ability to see when their friends are online, when they are typing, and when they last opened the programme. The last feature offered by WhatsApp is delivery notifications, which show when message is sent and when it reaches the recipient's device (Olaniyi , 2015).

Instagram

In its own words, Instagram is a "simple way to capture and share the world's moments." The smartphone app is being used by libraries all over the world to display a wide range of viewpoints. Libraries can offer a breath of fresh air with shelfies and images of literary delights amid an endless sea of selfish and food-related Instagram posts. Libraries present their interiors, exhibits, architecture, holdings, events, personnel, and patrons. A library's Instagram account posts pictures and videos that collectively depict the crucial function that libraries perform in their communities. Additionally, the account turns into a valuable marketing tool that may encourage visitors to consider the library as a destination (Kristine Techavanich ,2015).

MySpace

The blog, calendar, and individualized catalogue search features of this site have helped libraries increase their visibility in classroom settings. Starting from 2005

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through 2008, the most popular networking site was MySpace. MySpace is a free, advertisement-supported service that enables users to create "profile" pages on the Internet that include photos, a summary of their interests, and, most importantly, links to the profiles of other users.

Blogs

Occasionally, librarians may post messages, share what they've learned about a particular issue, and request that community members contribute to the discussion by posting relevant materials. Users will instantly react to articles and news regarding current events.

Wikis

It's a free, comprehensive online reference book that covers a wide range of subjects. The service acts as a hub where information may be accessed, altered, and expanded upon by interested parties. Together, the users of this site can produce excellent new pieces of web content.

LinkedIn

Librarians can utilize LinkedIn to put people in touch with subject matter specialists. Through this medium, librarians are able to extend their services to include ones such as Strategic Dissemination of Information (SDI).

Twitter

Use a micro blogging platform to keep your team and clients abreast of daily happenings, such as newly added or updated collections. Here, users can broadcast quick messages or status updates.

Library Thing

Instrument for enhancing library online catalogues. After creating an account on Library Thing, a list of ISBNs is sent to the service, and in return, a snippet of code is delivered that may be pasted into the online catalog's footer. Librarians can use this to notify readers of recent publications.

YouTube

Opening remarks, conferences, and workshops are just some of the events that have highlights streamed live on YouTube. The channel information part allows you to provide the name of your library, and the description field allows you to add details about your library's history, services, etc. You can be as specific as you like under personal information.

Flicker

With the use of this technology, librarians can share and disseminate up-to-date images of their collections with one another.(De Guzman et al., 2022) Recently published book and journal covers are available to Flicker users. Additionally, it can be used to educate its users on topical issues, such as the many graphics used as political party insignia in different countries.

Google Plus

Despite other social networking services such as Facebook and Twitter, the Google+ design team first attempted to emulate how people engage offline. Google Plus shifted gears in 2015, focusing more on the platform's popular interest-based communities. According to Google+ CEO David Busbies, the business is focused on "making communities even more central" to the programme. At the time, Google+ had

undergone a redesign that centered on Communities and Collections, which brought together material on certain topics. There were collections for cooking, do-it-yourself projects, and animals, among other things. There were Communities for various interests such as science fiction, parenting, and photography. If users are unable to find a suitable community or collection, they may create their own.

2. Benefits of social networking sites in Libraries

Social networking sites' benefits can be leveraged as the best instruments for offering library services to patrons. However, the majority of library patrons are unaware of these programmes. The users' awareness of these services can be raised by LIS professionals. The following services can be offered using the advantages of SNSs. Fewer studies focus on the services point of view, according to the LIS literature. This SNSs is being used slowly in Indian libraries. However, Hadagali and Kenchakkanavar (2016) attempted to provide detailed information about the potential library services that may be offered using these SNSs in their paper. In the bracket following the list of potential services, SNSs are mentioned.

1. SNSs like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube allow people to virtually visit libraries without physically going there.
2. SNSs give libraries the ability to direct visitors to videos, online tutorials, how-to guides for various devices, educational software, information about services, etc.
3. It gives students, researchers, and teachers a public platform where the information, improvement, application, and revision processes are fully visible

4. By displaying the news, SNSs can be used to promote library events or programmes.
5. enables the creation of online study groups for students at libraries (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube).
6. ‘Many users of libraries can benefit from the Ask a Librarian (reference service) feature on SNSs.
7. he library can use SNSs like YouTube, WhatsApp Facebook, Instagram and Twitter as a platform for user education or library orientation programmes, among other things.
8. NSs assist libraries in assisting patrons with the new publication of books, journals, and other reading resources.
9. SNSs assist in providing a service for newspaper clippings;
10. With the use of social networking access technologies (like Google Plus and Facebook), online reference services can be offered.
1. Users of Google Plus and Facebook can reserve, cancel, or renew their papers.
12. SNSs like Google Plus, Facebook, and Twitter let users offer feedback. and
13. SNSs (Google Plus, Facebook, Twitter) make it easier to get question paper banks.

3. Problems Use of Social Networking Sites (SNSs) on Library and Knowledge Center

An LIS professional's potential and reputation are in doubt in the age of information, where technology is undergoing rapid change. The most important issues in the twenty-first century are the growth in the number and quality of information access, as well as the simple and quick retrieval of information. LIS professionals have faced numerous difficulties as a result of web 2.0's influence and its tools in libraries. On the other hand, incorporating these new technologies into library activities would be a rare opportunity to demonstrate their existence and increase their exposure in the information world. In their study, Hadagali and Kenchakkanavar (2015) concentrate on the difficulties that social networking sites present.

An Library professional must be able to quickly access information that is easy to retrieve and disseminate;

2. An LIS professional must be knowledgeable about the most recent developments and technologies in the field, particularly web 2.0 and web 3.0 and its tools.

3. An Library professional must be able to assess how social networking sites might be used to enhance the services offered to users of libraries;

4. A Library professional must persuade management/authorities to supply the bare minimal infrastructure.

5. Making library resources accessible to users is a Library professional ultimate objective. SNSs should be actively pursued if they assist in achieving that goal;

6. **LIS professionals** should register on SNSs and provide the academic information users need to know;
7. A professional needs to keep an eye on SNS usage. Users may occasionally misuse the data.
8. These tasks must be handled by an experienced specialist. However, only a small number of institutions and businesses can afford it.
9. The experts must guarantee the difficulties pertaining to their personal data privacy on social networking sites.
10. To help users use SNSs more effectively, information literacy and orientation workshops should be periodically offered (Singh and Gill, 2015)

Conclusion :

Information is increasingly advancing quickly. Therefore, it is highly challenging to provide the correct and accurate information to the right user. However, this issue is lessened with the use of social networking or social networking websites. Social networking enables library staff to initially deliver information. That is why social networking sites are becoming more and more popular. Additionally, connecting with social networking sites helps the library gain popularity, which in turn attracts students and other users.

The smart phone are the devices to use these social media networking sites as well as social media apps are being used by libraries all over the world to display and get and share information e-books, e-journals, databases and a wide range of viewpoints and

information. Libraries can offer a breath of fresh air with shelf and images of literary delights amid an endless sea of information which includes new arrivals, new services at whatsapp, Instagram, twitter posts. Libraries present their interiors, exhibits, architecture, holdings, events, glimpses of seminars, workshops. and personnel, and patrons. A library's Instagram account posts pictures and videos that collectively depict the crucial function that libraries perform in academic setting.

It has been shown from the studies that some libraries use Twitter as a means of communicating with major information providers. Research shows that college students find using Facebook in library settings to be intriguing the Librarians can create awareness of these services to be provided to the users. Using SNSs. The benefits of SNSs can be analyzed by connecting to the academicians, stack-holders in educational institutions who get benefit from using these social networking sites (SNSs) According to the literature, there aren't as many publications that emphasise the services' point of view. SNSs are being adopted slowly in Pakistani libraries. In this context, Web 2.0 plays a significant role. The impact of Web 2.0 and its tools on libraries has presented several difficulties for LIS professionals. On the other hand, incorporating these new technologies into library activities would be a rare opportunity to demonstrate their existence and increase their exposure in the informationworld.

An LIS professional's job as an information facilitator requires quick, simple access to information retrieval and distribution. An LIS professional should be knowledgeable about the most recent developments in technology and social networking sites (SNSs), particularly web 2.0 and web 3.0, as well as their tools. They should also be able to assess how SNSs can be used to enhance the services that libraries offer their clients.

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